

Satellite Data (NRSC)

SPOT IMAGE

Scene Parameters

Part 3 of 3

CST 551
August 1996

Produced at Manchester Computing in accordance with an agreement between the Combined Higher Education Software Team (CHEST) and National Remote Sensing Centre Ltd. (NRSC)/SPOT IMAGE.

Satellite Data (NRSC)

SPOT IMAGE

Scene Parameters

Part 3 of 3

CST 551
August 1996

Produced at Manchester Computing in accordance with an agreement between the Combined Higher Education Software Team (CHEST) and National Remote Sensing Centre Ltd. (NRSC)/SPOT IMAGE.

Preface to the Manchester Reprint

This document is a straight reprint of the manual produced by National Remote Sensing Centre Ltd. (NRSC) and SPOT IMAGE.

We are grateful to NRSC and SPOT IMAGE for permission to reproduce this manual for the higher education and research community in the U.K.

Reprinted at Manchester Computing, University of Manchester.

INDEX

PART 3

CD-ROM Directories

In order of appearance

CD Number : 700006006
Order Number : 95052330
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 29-JUN-1995 14:23:09

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	1 009-241 89/04/18 12:01:06 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	02	Scene std.	1 010-240 88/04/09 11:52:44 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	03	Scene std.	1 010-243 87/12/01 11:53:59 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 3

CD Number : 7000005491
Order Number : 95052330
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 1-JUN-1995 08:24:19

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	09	Scene std.	2 013-238 91/01/31 11:54:02 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	10	Scene std.	2 013-239 91/01/31 11:54:10 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	08	Scene std.	1 022-239 89/12/03 11:57:32 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	12	Scene std.	2 013-241 92/11/28 11:29:09 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	13	Scene std.	2 013-242 91/01/31 11:54:35 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	07	Scene std.	1 017-240 86/11/06 11:53:56 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	06	Scene std.	1 017-239 86/11/06 11:53:47 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	05	Scene std.	1 014-241 88/11/24 11:49:49 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	04	Scene std.	1 014-240 88/11/24 11:49:41 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	11	Scene std.	2 013-240 92/11/28 11:29:01 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000005759
Order Number : 95052330
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:03:13

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	14	Scene std.	2 013-243 91/01/31 11:54:43 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	15	Scene std.	2 013-244 91/01/31 11:54:51 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	16	Scene std.	1 013-245 93/04/28 12:08:33 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	17	Scene std.	1 014-238 93/04/28 12:07:34 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	18	Scene std.	1 014-239 93/04/28 12:07:43 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	19	Scene std.	2 014-242 91/01/27 11:31:21 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	20	Scene std.	2 014-243 90/07/19 11:23:45 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	21	Scene std.	2 014-244 90/07/19 11:23:54 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	22	Scene std.	2 014-245 90/07/19 11:24:02 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	23	Scene std.	2 017-238 93/06/27 12:10:17 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000005519
Order Number : 95052330
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 1-JUN-1995 11:09:28

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	24	Scene std.	1 017-241 93/04/29 11:48:39 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	25	Scene std.	1 017-242 93/04/29 11:48:47 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	26	Scene std.	1 017-243 93/04/29 11:48:56 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	27	Scene std.	1 017-244 93/04/29 11:49:04 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	28	Scene std.	1 017-245 93/04/29 11:49:12 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	29	Scene std.	2 018-239 90/07/14 11:19:16 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	30	Scene std.	1 018-240 93/04/29 11:48:29 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	31	Scene std.	1 018-241 93/04/29 11:48:37 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	32	Scene std.	1 018-242 93/04/29 11:48:46 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	33	Scene std.	1 018-243 93/04/29 11:48:54 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000006008
Order Number : 95052330
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 29-JUN-1995 16:10:48

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description	
1	34	Scene std.	2 018-244 90/04/30 12:01:50 2 P Level 1B SAT 0	
2	35	Scene std.	2 021-239 94/03/17 11:10:57 1 P Level 1B SAT 0	
3	36	Scene std.	2 021-240 94/03/17 11:11:05 1 P Level 1B SAT 0	
4	37	Scene std.	2 022-239 94/02/17 11:49:27 2 P Level 1B SAT 0	
5	38	Scene std.	3 022-240 94/05/14 11:53:44 2 P Level 1B SAT 0	
6	39	Scene std.	2 026-239 90/11/20 11:38:48 1 P Level 1B SAT 0	
7	40	Scene std.	1 026-240 90/12/05 10:59:54 1 P Level 1B SAT 0	X
8	41	Scene std.	2 026-240 91/11/09 11:31:26 2 P Level 1B SAT 0	
9	42	Scene std.	2 029-239 90/12/01 11:27:08 2 P Level 1B SAT 0	
10	43	Scene std.	2 029-240 93/02/05 11:01:44 2 P Level 1B SAT 0	

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7001006614
Order Number : 95082428
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

Date : 25-AUG-1995 11:52:20

S P O T
I M A G E

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	2 026-241 95/08/02 11:37:54 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 1

CD Number : 700006675
Order Number : 95082428
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.
Date : 31-AUG-1995 09:07:48

S P O T
I M A G E

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	02	Scene std.	1 021-235 88/10/31 11:10:20 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 1

CD Number : 7000007153
Order Number : 95082428
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

Date : 25-AUG-1995 13:57:09

S P O T
I M A G E

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	03	Scene std.	3 022-243 95/06/29 11:49:45 2 P Level 1B SAT 1
2	04	Scene std.	1 024-246 89/07/16 11:50:17 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 2

CD Number : 7000008659

Date : 11-MAR-1996 08:75:39

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	1 026-240 90/12/05 10:59:54 1 P Level 1B

CD Number : 7001008820

Date : 11-MAR-1996 09:55:47

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	1 026-239 90/12/05 10:59:46 1 P Level 1B HRV 1
2	02	Scene std.	2 029-239 93/02/05 11:01:36 2 P Level 1B HRV 2
3	03	Scene std.	1 026-239 90/12/05 10:59:45 2 P Level 1B HRV 2
4	04	Scene std.	1 026-240 90/12/05 10:59:53 2 P Level 1B HRV 2

PART 3

CD Number : 7000006006
Order Number : 95052330
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 29-JUN-1995 14:23:09

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	1 009-241 89/04/18 12:01:06 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	02	Scene std.	1 010-240 88/04/09 11:52:44 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	03	Scene std.	1 010-243 87/12/01 11:53:59 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 3

Work order : 9505233001
 CD number : 700006006
 Scene ID : 1 9-241 89/04/18 12:01:06 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 29-JUN-1995 12:31:53

S P O T

 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 9-241 89/04/18 12:01:06 2 P
 K-J identification 9-241
 Date 89/04/18
 Time 12 h 01 mn 06 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 015.1 Degres
 Incidence angle L02.2 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +165.5 Elevation: 046.1
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.93283

Number of lines 6003
 Number of pixels per line 6244
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°39'17"
 Longitude W010°37'01"
 Pixel number 3116
 Line number 3000

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°58'56"	W010°55'17"	237	1
2	N053°50'25"	W010°02'22"	6244	1
3	N053°27'59"	W011°11'16"	1	6003
4	N053°19'34"	W010°18'58"	6008	6003

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6004	6003
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Work order : 9505233002
CD number : 7000006006
Scene ID : 1 10-240 88/04/09 11:52:44 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 29-JUN-1995 12:28:39

S P O T
IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 10-240 88/04/09 11:52:44 1 P
K-J identification 10-240
Date 88/04/09
Time 11 h 52 mn 44 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.5 Degres
Incidence angle R02.3 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +164.4 Elevation: 042.5
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.97559

Number of lines 6000
Number of pixels per line 6246
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'13"
Longitude W009°18'44"
Pixel number 3126
Line number 2999

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°26'44"	W009°37'38"	241	1
2	N054°18'34"	W008°43'59"	6246	1
3	N053°55'42"	W009°53'14"	1	6000
4	N053°47'39"	W009°00'13"	6006	6000

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6001	6000
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233003
 CD number : 7000006006
 Scene ID : 1 10-243 87/12/01 11:53:59 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 29-JUN-1995 12:33:16

S P O T
 ———
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 10-243 87/12/01 11:53:59 1 P
 K-J identification 10-243
 Date 87/12/01
 Time 11 h 53 mn 59 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 014.1 Degres
 Incidence angle R02.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +171.6 Elevation: 015.4
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.98574

Number of lines 6000
 Number of pixels per line 6253
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'15"
 Longitude W009°59'14"
 Pixel number 3132
 Line number 2999

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°02'41"	W010°17'43"	249	1
2	N052°54'46"	W009°25'43"	6253	1
3	N052°31'35"	W010°32'31"	1	6000
4	N052°23'46"	W009°41'06"	6005	6000

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6001	6000
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

SPOT1 HRV2 009-241/0 18 APR 89
P

N53°39' W010°37' 02"L 12H 01MN 07S N1B
BMA06812 CCTCONTROL @CNES1989

BMA06812

SPOT1 HRV1 010-240/0 09 APR 88
P

N54°07' / W009°19' 02°R 11H 52MN 44S N18
BMA06816 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

BMA06816

SPOT1 HRV1 010-243/0 01 DEC 87
P

NS2°43'W089°59' 02°R 11H 54MN 00S N1B
BTA16446 CCTCONTROL @CNES1987

BNA 06845

CD Number : 7000005491
Order Number : 95052330
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.
Date : 1-JUN-1995 08:24:19

S P O T
I M A G E

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	09	Scene std.	2 013-238 91/01/31 11:54:02 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	10	Scene std.	2 013-239 91/01/31 11:54:10 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	08	Scene std.	1 022-239 89/12/03 11:57:32 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	12	Scene std.	2 013-241 92/11/28 11:29:09 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	13	Scene std.	2 013-242 91/01/31 11:54:35 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	07	Scene std.	1 017-240 86/11/06 11:53:56 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	06	Scene std.	1 017-239 86/11/06 11:53:47 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	05	Scene std.	1 014-241 88/11/24 11:49:49 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	04	Scene std.	1 014-240 88/11/24 11:49:41 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	11	Scene std.	2 013-240 92/11/28 11:29:01 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505233009
CD number : 7000005491
Scene ID : 2 13-238 91/01/31 11:54:02 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 31-MAY-1995 16:24:56

S P O T
IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID : 2 13-238 91/01/31 11:54:02 1 P
K-J identification : 13-238
Date : 91/01/31
Time : 11 h 54 mn 02 s
Instrument : HRV1
Shift Along Track : 0
Processing level : 1B
Spectral mode : PAN
Number of spectral bands : 1
Spectral band indicators : PAN
Orientation angle : 015.7 Degres
Incidence angle : L02.5 Degres
Sun angles (degres) : Azimut: +167.4 Elevation: 016.7
Gain Number : 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) : 01.76453

Number of lines : 6004
Number of pixels per line : 6238
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record : byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude : N055°02'52"
Longitude : W007°48'13"
Pixel number : 3113
Line number : 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°22'38"	W008°06'48"	229	1
2	N055°13'47"	W007°12'12"	6238	1
3	N054°51'46"	W008°23'49"	1	6004
4	N054°43'03"	W007°29'52"	6010	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233010
CD number : 7000005491
Scene ID : 2 13-239 91/01/31 11:54:10 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 31-MAY-1995 16:20:29

S P O T
IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 13-239 91/01/31 11:54:10 1 P
K-J identification 13-239
Date 91/01/31
Time 11 h 54 mn 10 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 015.6 Degres
Incidence angle L02.5 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +167.2 Elevation: 017.1
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.76453

Number of lines 6004
Number of pixels per line 6239
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'04"
Longitude W008°03'43"
Pixel number 3114
Line number 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°54'48"	W008°22'10"	231	1
2	N054°46'03"	W007°28'09"	6239	1
3	N054°23'54"	W008°38'52"	1	6004
4	N054°15'17"	W007°45'28"	6009	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233008
CD number : 7000005491
Scene ID : 1 22-239 89/12/03 11:57:32 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 31-MAY-1995 16:23:22

SPOT
IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 22-239 89/12/03 11:57:32 2 P
K-J identification 22-239
Date 89/12/03
Time 11 h 57 mn 32 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 020.9 Degres
Incidence angle L29.6 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +179.3 Elevation: 013.6
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.91430

Number of lines 6013
Number of pixels per line 8007
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'05"
Longitude W002°46'29"
Pixel number 3915
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°57'19"	W003°08'55"	205	1
2	N054°42'12"	W002°00'57"	8007	1
3	N054°27'20"	W003°30'14"	1	6013
4	N054°12'26"	W002°22'58"	7803	6013

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6014	6013
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233012
CD number : 7000005491
Scene ID : 2 13-241 92/11/28 11:29:09 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 31-MAY-1995 16:36:39

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 13-241 92/11/28 11:29:09 1 P
K-J Identification 13-241
Date 92/11/28
Time 11 h 29 mn 09 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 009.7 Degres
Incidence angle R28.3 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +167.4 Elevation: 014.3
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.67470

Number of lines 5969
Number of pixels per line 7874
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°39'19"
Longitude W008°20'08"
Pixel number 4017
Line number 2982

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°58'30"	W008°49'22"	265	1
2	N053°51'34"	W007°40'53"	7874	1
3	N053°27'00"	W009°00'26"	1	5969
4	N053°20'08"	W007°52'47"	7610	5969

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5970	5969
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233013
CD number : 7000005491
Scene ID : 2 13-242 91/01/31 11:54:35 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 31-MAY-1995 16:33:26

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 13-242 91/01/31 11:54:35 1 P
K-J identification 13-242
Date 91/01/31
Time 11 h 54 mn 35 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 015.0 Degres
Incidence angle L02.5 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.4 Elevation: 018.4
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.76453

Number of lines 6004
Number of pixels per line 6247
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°11'18"
Longitude W008°48'32"
Pixel number 3117
Line number 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°30'55"	W009°06'38"	241	1
2	N053°22'28"	W008°14'17"	6247	1
3	N052°59'57"	W009°22'23"	1	6004
4	N052°51'36"	W008°30'37"	6007	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233007
CD number : 7000005491
Scene ID : 1 17-240 86/11/06 11:53:56 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 31-MAY-1995 16:11:25

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 17-240 86/11/06 11:53:56 1 P
K-J identification 17-240
Date 86/11/06
Time 11 h 53 mn 56 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.9 Degres
Incidence angle L11.3 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +176.0 Elevation: 020.0
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.01110

Number of lines 6007
Number of pixels per line 6454
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'13"
Longitude W006°27'39"
Pixel number 3203
Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°27'20"	W006°45'53"	227	1
2	N054°17'30"	W005°50'56"	6454	1
3	N053°56'40"	W007°03'38"	1	6007
4	N053°46'57"	W006°09'17"	6228	6007

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6008	6007
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233006
CD number : 7000005491
Scene ID : 1 17-239 86/11/06 11:53:47 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 31-MAY-1995 16:12:51

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 17-239 86/11/06 11:53:47 1 P
K-J identification 17-239
Date 86/11/06
Time 11 h 53 mn 47 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 017.1 Degres
Incidence angle L11.3 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +176.3 Elevation: 019.6
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.01110

Number of lines 6007
Number of pixels per line 6453
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'05"
Longitude W006°11'02"
Pixel number 3201
Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°55'15"	W006°29'23"	225	1
2	N054°45'17"	W005°33'51"	6453	1
3	N054°24'36"	W006°47'29"	1	6007
4	N054°14'46"	W005°52'35"	6229	6007

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6008	6007
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233005
CD number : 7000005491
Scene ID : 1 14-241 88/11/24 11:49:49 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 31-MAY-1995 16:08:52

S P O T
 —————
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID : 1 14-241 88/11/24 11:49:49 2 P
K-J identification : 14-241
Date : 88/11/24
Time : 11 h 49 mn 49 s
Instrument : HRV2
Shift Along Track : 0
Processing level : 1B
Spectral mode : PAN
Number of spectral bands : 1
Spectral band indicators : PAN
Orientation angle : 015.4 Degres
Incidence angle : L03.6 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) : Azimut: +173.5 Elevation: 015.7
Gain Number : 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) : 00.94798

Number of lines : 6004
Number of pixels per line : 6254
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record : byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude : N053°39'17"
Longitude : W007°21'20"
Pixel number : 3120
Line number : 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°58'59"	W007°39'29"	235	1
2	N053°50'18"	W006°46'32"	6254	1
3	N053°28'05"	W007°55'43"	1	6004
4	N053°19'30"	W007°03'22"	6020	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233004
CD number : 7000005491
Scene ID : 1 14-240 88/11/24 11:49:41 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 31-MAY-1995 16:11:39

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 14-240 88/11/24 11:49:41 2 P
K-J identification 14-240
Date 88/11/24
Time 11 h 49 mn 41 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 015.6 Degres
Incidence angle L03.6 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +173.8 Elevation: 015.2
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94798

Number of lines 6004
Number of pixels per line 6253
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'13"
Longitude W007°06'13"
Pixel number 3118
Line number 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°26'57"	W007°24'29"	233	1
2	N054°18'10"	W006°30'59"	6253	1
3	N053°56'04"	W007°41'02"	1	6004
4	N053°47'24"	W006°48'08"	6021	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233011
CD number : 7000005491
Scene ID : 2 13-240 92/11/28 11:29:01 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 31-MAY-1995 16:24:41

Scene parameters

Scene ID : 2 13-240 92/11/28 11:29:01 1 P
K-J identification : 13-240
Date : 92/11/28
Time : 11 h 29 mn 01 s
Instrument : HRV1
Shift Along Track : 0
Processing level : 1B
Spectral mode : PAN
Number of spectral bands : 1
Spectral band indicators : PAN
Orientation angle : 009.8 Degres
Incidence angle : R28.3 Degres
Sun angles (degres) : Azimut: +167.6 Elevation: 013.9
Gain Number : 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) : 01.67470

Number of lines : 5969
Number of pixels per line : 7873
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record : byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude : N054°07'14"
Longitude : W008°09'52"
Pixel number : 4016
Line number : 2982

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°26'27"	W008°39'23"	263	1
2	N054°19'27"	W007°30'09"	7873	1
3	N053°54'57"	W008°50'37"	1	5969
4	N053°48'02"	W007°42'14"	7611	5969

Files parameters

Volume directory	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5970	5969
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT2 HRV1 013-238/0 31 JAN 91
P

N55°03' / W007°48' 02"L 11H 54MN 02S N18
BMA06849 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA06849

SPOT2 HRV1 013-239/0 31 JAN 91
P

N54°35' / W008°04' 02"L 11H 54MN 10S N1B
BMA06850 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA06850

SPOT1 HRV2 022-239/0 03 DEC 89
P

N54°35' / U002°46' 29°L 11H 57MN 325 N1E
BMA09468 CCTCONTROL @CNES1989

BMA09468

BMA1512

SPOT2 HRV1 013-241/0 28 NOV 92
P

N53°39' W008°20' 28°R 11H 29MN 09S N1B
BMA01512 CCTCONTROL @CNES1992

SPOT2 HRV1 013-242/0 31 JAN 91
P

N53°11' / W008°49' 02"L 11H 54MN 35S N1B
BMA06875 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA06875

DATA 5/100

SPOT 1 HRV 1 017-240 06 NOV 86
P

N54°07' W006°28' 11"L 11H 53MN 56S N1B
ST028607 CCTCONTROL @CNES1987

NOV 06 1986
215
215

SPOT 1 HRV 1 017-239 06 NOV 86
P

NS4°35'W086°11' 11°L 11H 53MN 47S M1B
ST014310 CCTCONTROL @CNES1986

SPOT1 HRV2 014-241/0 24 NOV 88
P

N53°39'W007°21' 03"L 11H 49MN 50S N1B
BMA06847 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

BMA06847

SPOT1 HRV2 014-240/0 24 NOV 88
P

NS4°07'W007°06' 03°L 11H 49MN 42S N1B
BMA06846 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

BMA06846

BMA 1497

SPOT2 HRV1 013-240/0 28 NOV 92
P

N54°07' W008°10' 28°R 11H 29MN 01S N1B
BMA01497 CCTCONTROL @CNES1992

CD Number : 7000005759
Order Number : 95052330
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:03:13

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	14	Scene std.	2 013-243 91/01/31 11:54:43 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	15	Scene std.	2 013-244 91/01/31 11:54:51 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	16	Scene std.	1 013-245 93/04/28 12:08:33 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	17	Scene std.	1 014-238 93/04/28 12:07:34 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	18	Scene std.	1 014-239 93/04/28 12:07:43 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	19	Scene std.	2 014-242 91/01/27 11:31:21 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	20	Scene std.	2 014-243 90/07/19 11:23:45 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	21	Scene std.	2 014-244 90/07/19 11:23:54 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	22	Scene std.	2 014-245 90/07/19 11:24:02 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	23	Scene std.	2 017-238 93/06/27 12:10:17 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505233014
CD number : 7000005759
Scene ID : 2 13-243 91/01/31 11:54:43 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:25:36

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 13-243 91/01/31 11:54:43 1 P
K-J identification 13-243
Date 91/01/31
Time 11 h 54 mn 43 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.9 Degres
Incidence angle L02.5 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +166.2 Elevation: 018.8
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.76453

Number of lines 6004
Number of pixels per line 6248
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'15"
Longitude W009°02'57"
Pixel number 3119
Line number 3001

Comers Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°02'50"	W009°20'56"	243	1
2	N052°54'29"	W008°29'07"	6248	1
3	N052°31'51"	W009°36'24"	1	6004
4	N052°23'35"	W008°45'09"	6006	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233015
CD number : 7000005759
Scene ID : 2 13-244 91/01/31 11:54:51 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:27:13

SPOT
IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 13-244 91/01/31 11:54:51 1 P
K-J identification 13-244
Date 91/01/31
Time 11 h 54 mn 51 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.7 Degres
Incidence angle L02.5 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.0 Elevation: 019.3
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.76453

Number of lines 6004
Number of pixels per line 6249
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'08"
Longitude W009°17'07"
Pixel number 3120
Line number 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°34'42"	W009°34'59"	245	1
2	N052°26'26"	W008°43'41"	6249	1
3	N052°03'40"	W009°50'11"	1	6004
4	N051°55'30"	W008°59'26"	6005	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233016
 CD number : 7000005759
 Scene ID : 1 13-245 93/04/28 12:08:33 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:27:22

S P O T

 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 13-245 93/04/28 12:08:33 1 P
 K-J identification 13-245
 Date 93/04/28
 Time 12 h 08 mn 33 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 017.9 Degres
 Incidence angle L22.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +169.6 Elevation: 051.7
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.50967

 Number of lines 6012
 Number of pixels per line 7167
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°46'59"
 Longitude W009°20'57"
 Pixel number 3528
 Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°07'51"	W009°40'20"	231	1
2	N051°56'16"	W008°42'41"	7167	1
3	N051°37'19"	W009°58'02"	1	6012
4	N051°25'53"	W009°00'57"	6937	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233017
 CD number : 7000005759
 Scene ID : 1 14-238 93/04/28 12:07:34 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:28:48

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 14-238 93/04/28 12:07:34 1 P
 K-J identification 14-238
 Date 93/04/28
 Time 12 h 07 mn 34 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 019.6 Degres
 Incidence angle L22.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +173.0 Elevation: 048.7
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.50967

Number of lines 6012
 Number of pixels per line 7153
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°02'53"
 Longitude W007°16'10"
 Pixel number 3521
 Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°24'05"	W007°36'12"	211	1
2	N055°11'29"	W006°34'28"	7153	1
3	N054°53'52"	W007°56'36"	1	6012
4	N054°41'25"	W006°55'33"	6943	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233018
CD number : 7000005759
Scene ID : 1 14-239 93/04/28 12:07:43 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:37:11

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 14-239 93/04/28 12:07:43 1 P
K-J identification 14-239
Date 93/04/28
Time 12 h 07 mn 43 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 019.3 Degres
Incidence angle L22.3 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +172.5 Elevation: 049.1
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.50967

Number of lines 6012
Number of pixels per line 7156
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'06"
Longitude W007°35'05"
Pixel number 3523
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°56'15"	W007°55'01"	215	1
2	N054°43'48"	W006°53'54"	7156	1
3	N054°25'58"	W008°14'59"	1	6012
4	N054°13'41"	W007°14'32"	6942	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233019
CD number : 7000005759
Scene ID : 2 14-242 91/01/27 11:31:21 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:38:53

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 14-242 91/01/27 11:31:21 1 P
K-J identification 14-242
Date 91/01/27
Time 11 h 31 mn 21 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 010.9 Degres
Incidence angle R21.3 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +162.0 Elevation: 016.6
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.76453

Number of lines 5980
Number of pixels per line 7114
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°11'18"
Longitude W007°52'40"
Pixel number 3608
Line number 2988

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°30'29"	W008°17'16"	263	1
2	N053°23'28"	W007°16'32"	7114	1
3	N052°59'04"	W008°29'22"	1	5980
4	N052°52'07"	W007°29'22"	6852	5980

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5981	5980
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233020
CD number : 7000005759
Scene ID : 2 14-243 90/07/19 11:23:45 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:39:03

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 14-243 90/07/19 11:23:45 1 P
K-J identification 14-243
Date 90/07/19
Time 11 h 23 mn 45 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 009.1 Degres
Incidence angle R30.4 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +148.2 Elevation: 055.3
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.37760

Number of lines 5966
Number of pixels per line 8180
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'07"
Longitude W008°13'09"
Pixel number 4181
Line number 2980

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°02'16"	W008°43'26"	273	1
2	N052°55'29"	W007°33'43"	8180	1
3	N052°30'43"	W008°53'48"	1	5966
4	N052°23'59"	W007°44'54"	7908	5966

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5967	5966
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233021
CD number : 7000005759
Scene ID : 2 14-244 90/07/19 11:23:54 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:40:55

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 14-244 90/07/19 11:23:54 1 P
K-J identification 14-244
Date 90/07/19
Time 11 h 23 mn 54 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 009.1 Degres
Incidence angle R30.4 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +147.7 Elevation: 055.7
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.37760

Number of lines 5966
Number of pixels per line 8181
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'01"
Longitude W008°22'42"
Pixel number 4181
Line number 2980

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°34'08"	W008°52'41"	275	1
2	N052°27'24"	W007°43'42"	8181	1
3	N052°02'35"	W009°02'55"	1	5966
4	N051°55'54"	W007°54'44"	7907	5966

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5967	5966
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233022
CD number : 7000005759
Scene ID : 2 14-245 90/07/19 11:24:02 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:51:38

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 14-245 90/07/19 11:24:02 1 P
K-J identification 14-245
Date 90/07/19
Time 11 h 24 mn 02 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 009.0 Degres
Incidence angle R30.4 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +147.1 Elevation: 056.0
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.37760

Number of lines 5966
Number of pixels per line 8182
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°46'50"
Longitude W008°32'08"
Pixel number 4182
Line number 2980

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°05'56"	W009°01'50"	277	1
2	N051°59'15"	W007°53'34"	8182	1
3	N051°34'23"	W009°11'55"	1	5966
4	N051°27'45"	W008°04'26"	7906	5966

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5967	5966
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233023
CD number : 7000005759
Scene ID : 2 17-238 93/06/27 12:10:17 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:53:18

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 17-238 93/06/27 12:10:17 2 P
K-J identification 17-238
Date 93/06/27
Time 12 h 10 mn 17 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 020.5 Degres
Incidence angle L26.8 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +172.7 Elevation: 058.2
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.55618

Number of lines 6013
Number of pixels per line 7640
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N055°02'53"
Longitude W006°08'12"
Pixel number 3746
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N055°24'42"	W006°29'39"	207	1
2	N055°10'35"	W005°23'57"	7640	1
3	N054°54'39"	W006°50'52"	1	6013
4	N054°40'44"	W005°45'52"	7434	6013

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6014	6013
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT2 HRV1 013-243/0 31 JAN 91

F

N52°43'W009°03' 02°L 11H 54MN 43S N18
BMA06892 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA06892

SPOT2 HRV1 013-244/0 31 JAN 91
P

N52°15' W009°17' 02"L 11H 54MN 51S N1B
BMA06902 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA06902

SPOT1 HRV1 013-245/0 28 APR 93
P

N51°47' / W009°21' 22"L 12H 00MN 33S N18
BMA06903 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06903

SPOT1 HRV1 014-238/0 28 APR 93
P

N55°03'W007°16' 22°L 12H 07MN 34S N1B
BMA06908 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06908

SPOT1 HRV1 014-239/0 28 APR 93
P

N54°35' / W007°35' 22°L 12H 07MN 43S N1B
BMA06909 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA 06909

SPOT2 HRV1 014-242/0 27 JAN 91
P

N53°11' / W007°53' 21°P 11H 31MN 21S N1B
BMA06910 CCTCONTROL @CHES1991

BMA06910

SPOT2 HRV1 014-243/0 19 JUL 90

P

N52°43'14000°13' 30°R 11H 23MN 465 N1B

BMA06911

CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA06911

SPOT2 HRV1 014-244/0 19 JUL 90
P

N52°15' W008°23' 30°R 11H 23MN 54S N1B
BMA06912 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA06912

SPOT2 HRV1 014-245/0 19 JUL 90
P

N51°47' / W88°32' 30°R 11H 24MN 02S N1B
BMA06913 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA06913

SPOT2 HRV2 017-238/0 27 JUN 93
P

N55°03'W006°08' 26°L 12H 10MN 17S N1B
BMA06914 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06914

CD Number : 7000005519
Order Number : 95052330
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 1-JUN-1995 11:09:28

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	24	Scene std.	1 017-241 93/04/29 11:48:39 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	25	Scene std.	1 017-242 93/04/29 11:48:47 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	26	Scene std.	1 017-243 93/04/29 11:48:56 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	27	Scene std.	1 017-244 93/04/29 11:49:04 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	28	Scene std.	1 017-245 93/04/29 11:49:12 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	29	Scene std.	2 018-239 90/07/14 11:19:16 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	30	Scene std.	1 018-240 93/04/29 11:48:29 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	31	Scene std.	1 018-241 93/04/29 11:48:37 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	32	Scene std.	1 018-242 93/04/29 11:48:46 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	33	Scene std.	1 018-243 93/04/29 11:48:54 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505233024
CD number : 7000005519
Scene ID : 1 17-241 93/04/29 11:48:39 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 10:02:24

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 17-241 93/04/29 11:48:39 1 P
K-J identification 17-241
Date 93/04/29
Time 11 h 48 mn 39 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 015.9 Degres
Incidence angle L06.6 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.5 Elevation: 049.9
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.88936

Number of lines 6006
Number of pixels per line 6305
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°39'19"
Longitude W006°45'39"
Pixel number 3139
Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°59'08"	W007°03'40"	235	1
2	N053°50'06"	W006°10'24"	6305	1
3	N053°28'18"	W007°20'21"	1	6006
4	N053°19'23"	W006°27'41"	6071	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233025
CD number : 7000005519
Scene ID : 1 17-242 93/04/29 11:48:47 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 10:03:14

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 17-242 93/04/29 11:48:47 1 P
K-J identification 17-242
Date 93/04/29
Time 11 h 48 mn 47 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 015.7 Degres
Incidence angle L06.6 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.0 Elevation: 050.3
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.88936

Number of lines 6006
Number of pixels per line 6309
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°11'19"
Longitude W007°00'56"
Pixel number 3141
Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°31'07"	W007°18'51"	239	1
2	N053°22'11"	W006°26'07"	6309	1
3	N053°00'15"	W007°35'13"	1	6006
4	N052°51'26"	W006°43'05"	6071	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233026
CD number : 7000005519
Scene ID : 1 17-243 93/04/29 11:48:56 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 10:02:18

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 17-243 93/04/29 11:48:56 1 P
K-J identification 17-243
Date 93/04/29
Time 11 h 48 mn 56 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 015.6 Degres
Incidence angle L06.6 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +165.5 Elevation: 050.8
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.88936

Number of lines 6006
Number of pixels per line 6310
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'16"
Longitude W007°15'58"
Pixel number 3140
Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°03'02"	W007°33'46"	241	1
2	N052°54'12"	W006°41'34"	6310	1
3	N052°32'08"	W007°49'50"	1	6006
4	N052°23'25"	W006°58'13"	6070	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233027
CD number : 7000005519
Scene ID : 1 17-244 93/04/29 11:49:04 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 10:03:52

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 17-244 93/04/29 11:49:04 1 P
K-J identification 17-244
Date 93/04/29
Time 11 h 49 mn 04 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 015.4 Degres
Incidence angle L06.6 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +165.1 Elevation: 051.2
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.88936

Number of lines 6006
Number of pixels per line 6311
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'09"
Longitude W007°30'43"
Pixel number 3142
Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°34'53"	W007°48'25"	243	1
2	N052°26'09"	W006°56'45"	6311	1
3	N052°03'58"	W008°04'12"	1	6006
4	N051°55'20"	W007°13'05"	6069	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233028
CD number : 700005519
Scene ID : 1 17-245 93/04/29 11:49:12 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 10:13:37

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID : 1 17-245 93/04/29 11:49:12 1 P
K-J identification : 17-245
Date : 93/04/29
Time : 11 h 49 mn 12 s
Instrument : HRV1
Shift Along Track : 0
Processing level : 1B
Spectral mode : PAN
Number of spectral bands : 1
Spectral band indicators : PAN
Orientation angle : 015.2 Degres
Incidence angle : L06.6 Degres
Sun angles (degres) : Azimut: +164.6 Elevation: 051.6
Gain Number : 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) : 00.88936

Number of lines : 6006
Number of pixels per line : 6314
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record : byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude : N051°46'59"
Longitude : W007°45'14"
Pixel number : 3143
Line number : 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°06'41"	W008°02'49"	247	1
2	N051°58'03"	W007°11'39"	6314	1
3	N051°35'44"	W008°18'19"	1	6006
4	N051°27'12"	W007°27'41"	6068	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233029
CD number : 7000005519
Scene ID : 2 18-239 90/07/14 11:19:16 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 10:08:13

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 18-239 90/07/14 11:19:16 1 P
K-J identification 18-239
Date 90/07/14
Time 11 h 19 mn 16 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 010.3 Degres
Incidence angle R26.2 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +151.7 Elevation: 054.9
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.37760

Number of lines 5972
Number of pixels per line 7610
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°34'55"
Longitude W005°32'07"
Pixel number 3875
Line number 2984

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°54'11"	W006°00'25"	259	1
2	N054°47'02"	W004°52'53"	7610	1
3	N054°22'42"	W006°12'16"	1	5972
4	N054°15'41"	W005°05'33"	7352	5972

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5973	5972
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233030
CD number : 7000005519
Scene ID : 1 18-240 93/04/29 11:48:29 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 10:12:26

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 18-240 93/04/29 11:48:29 2 P
K-J identification 18-240
Date 93/04/29
Time 11 h 48 mn 29 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.7 Degres
Incidence angle L09.7 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +167.9 Elevation: 049.6
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.85705

Number of lines 6008
Number of pixels per line 6389
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'14"
Longitude W005°50'56"
Pixel number 3174
Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°27'16"	W006°09'05"	227	1
2	N054°17'40"	W005°14'38"	6389	1
3	N053°56'33"	W006°26'36"	1	6008
4	N053°47'04"	W005°32'45"	6163	6008

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6009	6008
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233031
 CD number : 7000005519
 Scene ID : 1 18-241 93/04/29 11:48:37 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 1-JUN-1995 10:14:19

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 18-241 93/04/29 11:48:37 2 P
 K-J identification 18-241
 Date 93/04/29
 Time 11 h 48 mn 37 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 016.5 Degres
 Incidence angle L09.7 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +167.4 Elevation: 050.0
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.85705

Number of lines 6008
 Number of pixels per line 6390
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°39'18"
 Longitude W006°06'59"
 Pixel number 3174
 Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°59'19"	W006°25'02"	229	1
2	N053°49'49"	W005°31'08"	6390	1
3	N053°28'33"	W006°42'12"	1	6008
4	N053°19'11"	W005°48'54"	6162	6008

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6009	6008
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233032
CD number : 7000005519
Scene ID : 1 18-242 93/04/29 11:48:46 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 1-JUN-1995 10:22:38

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 18-242 93/04/29 11:48:46 2 P
K-J identification 18-242
Date 93/04/29
Time 11 h 48 mn 46 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.3 Degres
Incidence angle L09.7 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +167.0 Elevation: 050.4
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.85705

Number of lines 6008
Number of pixels per line 6393
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°11'19"
Longitude W006°22'45"
Pixel number 3175
Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°31'17"	W006°40'41"	233	1
2	N053°21'54"	W005°47'20"	6393	1
3	N053°00'30"	W006°57'31"	1	6008
4	N052°51'14"	W006°04'45"	6161	6008

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6009	6008
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233033
 CD number : 7000005519
 Scene ID : 1 18-243 93/04/29 11:48:54 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 1-JUN-1995 10:27:12

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 18-243 93/04/29 11:48:54 2 P
 K-J identification 18-243
 Date 93/04/29
 Time 11 h 48 mn 54 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 016.1 Degres
 Incidence angle L09.7 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.5 Elevation: 050.9
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.85705

Number of lines 6008
 Number of pixels per line 6395
 Row of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'16"
 Longitude W006°38'13"
 Pixel number 3177
 Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°03'12"	W006°56'03"	235	1
2	N052°53'56"	W006°03'14"	6395	1
3	N052°32'23"	W007°12'34"	1	6008
4	N052°23'14"	W006°20'19"	6161	6008

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6009	6008
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT1 HRV1 017-241/0 29 APR 93
P

BMA4482

N53°39' W006°46' 06°L 11H 48MIN 39S N1E
BMA04482 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA04482

SPOT1 HRV1 017-242/0 29 APR 93
P

N53°11'W007°01' 06"L 11H 48MN 47S N1B
BMA05671 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA05671

SPOT1 HRV1 017-243/0 29 APR 93
P

N52°43'W007°16' 06°L 11H 48MN 565 N1E
BMA05733 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA05733

SPOT1 HRV1 017-244/0 29 APR 93
P

N52°15' W007°31' 06°L 11H 49MN 04S N1B
BMA06915 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06915

SPOT1 HRV1 017-245/0 29 APR 93
P

N51°47' / W087°45' 06"L 11H 49MN 12S N1B
BMA06916 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06916

SPOT1 HRVZ 018-240/0 29 APR 93
P

N54°07' / W005°51' 09"L 11H 48MN 29S N1B
BMA06917 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06917

SPOT1 HRV2 018-241/0 29 APR 93
P

N53°39' / W006°07' 09"L 11H 48MN 37S N18
BMA06918 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06918

SPOT1 HRV2 018-242/0 29 APR 93
P

N53°11' W006°23' 09"L 11H 48MN 46S N1B
BMA05693 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA05693

SPOT1 HRV2 018-243/0 29 APR 93
P

N52°43'W005°38' 09"L 11H 48MN 54S N1B
BMA05734 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA05734

CD Number : 700006008
Order Number : 95052330
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 29-JUN-1995 16:10:48

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	34	Scene std.	2 018-244 90/04/30 12:01:50 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	35	Scene std.	2 021-239 94/03/17 11:10:57 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	36	Scene std.	2 021-240 94/03/17 11:11:05 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	37	Scene std.	2 022-239 94/02/17 11:49:27 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	38	Scene std.	3 022-240 94/05/14 11:53:44 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	39	Scene std.	2 026-239 90/11/20 11:38:48 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	40	Scene std.	1 026-240 90/12/05 10:59:54 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	41	Scene std.	2 026-240 91/11/09 11:31:26 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	42	Scene std.	2 029-239 90/12/01 11:27:08 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	43	Scene std.	2 029-240 93/02/05 11:01:44 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

×

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505233034
 CD number : 7000006008
 Scene ID : 2 18-244 90/04/30 12:01:50 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 29-JUN-1995 11:23:33

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 18-244 90/04/30 12:01:50 2 P
 K-J identification 18-244
 Date 90/04/30
 Time 12 h 01 mn 50 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 018.5 Degres
 Incidence angle L24.1 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +171.3 Elevation: 052.0
 Gain Number 6
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.29354

Number of lines 6013
 Number of pixels per line 7345
 Row of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°14'54"
 Longitude W006°40'26"
 Pixel number 3610
 Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°36'01"	W007°00'25"	229	1
2	N052°23'47"	W006°00'50"	7345	1
3	N052°05'35"	W007°18'44"	1	6013
4	N051°53'30"	W006°19'45"	7117	6013

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6014	6013
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233035
 CD number : 7000006008
 Scene ID : 2 21-239 94/03/17 11:10:57 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 29-JUN-1995 11:20:50

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 21-239 94/03/17 11:10:57 1 P
 K-J identification 21-239
 Date 94/03/17
 Time 11 h 10 mn 57 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 009.6 Degres
 Incidence angle R29.7 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +157.7 Elevation: 031.5
 Gain Number 8
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65634

Number of lines 5967
 Number of pixels per line 8062
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'06"
 Longitude W004°26'29"
 Pixel number 4118
 Line number 2981

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°54'19"	W004°57'26"	261	1
2	N054°47'19"	W003°45'36"	8062	1
3	N054°22'49"	W005°08'33"	1	5967
4	N054°15'52"	W003°57'37"	7802	5967

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5968	5967
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233036
CD number : 7000006008
Scene ID : 2 21-240 94/03/17 11:11:05 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 29-JUN-1995 11:25:04

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 21-240 94/03/17 11:11:05 1 P
K-J identification 21-240
Date 94/03/17
Time 11 h 11 mn 05 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 009.5 Degres
Incidence angle R29.7 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +157.4 Elevation: 031.9
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65634

Number of lines 5967
Number of pixels per line 8063
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'14"
Longitude W004°36'39"
Pixel number 4118
Line number 2981

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°26'27"	W005°07'17"	263	1
2	N054°19'29"	W003°56'15"	8063	1
3	N053°54'56"	W005°18'13"	1	5967
4	N053°48'02"	W004°08'04"	7801	5967

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5968	5967
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233037
 CD number : 7000006008
 Scene ID : 2 22-239 94/02/17 11:49:27 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 29-JUN-1995 11:23:43

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 22-239 94/02/17 11:49:27 2 P
 K-J identification 22-239
 Date 94/02/17
 Time 11 h 49 mn 27 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 018.8 Degres
 Incidence angle L19.9 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +170.0 Elevation: 022.7
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.53899

Number of lines 6011
 Number of pixels per line 6960
 Row of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'06"
 Longitude W003°14'53"
 Pixel number 3432
 Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°55'59"	W003°34'18"	217	1
2	N054°44'11"	W002°34'45"	6960	1
3	N054°25'37"	W003°53'52"	1	6011
4	N054°13'59"	W002°54'58"	6744	6011

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6012	6011
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233038
CD number : 7000006008
Scene ID : 3 22-240 94/05/14 11:53:44 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 29-JUN-1995 11:37:45

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 3 22-240 94/05/14 11:53:44 2 P
K-J identification 22-240
Date 94/05/14
Time 11 h 53 mn 44 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 019.3 Degres
Incidence angle L24.1 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +173.2 Elevation: 054.2
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.61395

Number of lines 6012
Number of pixels per line 7341
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'14"
Longitude W003°33'10"
Pixel number 3607
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°28'32"	W003°53'33"	221	1
2	N054°15'44"	W002°51'36"	7341	1
3	N053°58'16"	W004°13'24"	1	6012
4	N053°45'38"	W003°12'06"	7121	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233039
 CD number : 7000006008
 Scene ID : 2 26-239 90/11/20 11:38:48 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 29-JUN-1995 11:35:09

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-239 90/11/20 11:38:48 1 P
 K-J identification 26-239
 Date 90/11/20
 Time 11 h 38 mn 48 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 017.7 Degres
 Incidence angle L14.1 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +176.6 Elevation: 016.0
 Gain Number 8
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.78691

Number of lines 6009
 Number of pixels per line 6576
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'04"
 Longitude W001°42'32"
 Pixel number 3256
 Line number 3004

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°55'27"	W002°01'04"	221	1
2	N054°44'58"	W001°04'35"	6576	1
3	N054°24'53"	W002°19'38"	1	6009
4	N054°14'33"	W001°23'46"	6356	6009

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6010	6009
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233040
CD number : 7000006008
Scene ID : 2 26-240 90/11/20 11:38:57 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 29-JUN-1995 11:39:31

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-240 90/11/20 11:38:57 1 P
K-J identification 26-240
Date 90/11/20
Time 11 h 38 mn 57 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 017.5 Degres
Incidence angle L14.1 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +176.4 Elevation: 016.4
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.78691

Number of lines 6009
Number of pixels per line 6577
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'13"
Longitude W001°59'36"
Pixel number 3258
Line number 3004

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°27'32"	W002°18'02"	223	1
2	N054°17'11"	W001°22'07"	6577	1
3	N053°56'57"	W002°36'13"	1	6009
4	N053°46'44"	W001°40'56"	6355	6009

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6010	6009
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233041
CD number : 7000006008
Scene ID : 2 26-240 91/11/09 11:31:26 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 29-JUN-1995 11:37:56

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-240 91/11/09 11:31:26 2 P
K-J Identification 26-240
Date 91/11/09
Time 11 h 31 mn 26 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.0 Degres
Incidence angle L06.3 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +175.2 Elevation: 019.1
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.64216

Number of lines 6006
Number of pixels per line 6303
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'13"
Longitude W001°38'55"
Pixel number 3138
Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°27'04"	W001°57'05"	233	1
2	N054°17'58"	W001°03'15"	6303	1
3	N053°56'15"	W002°14'03"	1	6006
4	N053°47'16"	W001°20'50"	6071	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233042
CD number : 7000006008
Scene ID : 2 29-239 90/12/01 11:27:08 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 29-JUN-1995 11:50:56

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 29-239 90/12/01 11:27:08 2 P
K-J identification 29-239
Date 90/12/01
Time 11 h 27 mn 08 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.0 Degres
Incidence angle L04.9 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +174.1 Elevation: 013.7
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65649

Number of lines 6005
Number of pixels per line 6276
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'05"
Longitude W000°44'45"
Pixel number 3128
Line number 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°54'54"	W001°03'05"	231	1
2	N054°45'52"	W000°08'51"	6276	1
3	N054°24'05"	W001°20'10"	1	6005
4	N054°15'10"	W000°26'34"	6046	6005

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6006	6005
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505233043
 CD number : 7000006008
 Scene ID : 2 29-240 93/02/05 11:01:44 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 29-JUN-1995 11:48:59

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 29-240 93/02/05 11:01:44 2 P
 K-J Identification 29-240
 Date 93/02/05
 Time 11 h 01 mn 44 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 010.4 Degrees
 Incidence angle R25.1 Degrees
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +161.2 Elevation: 018.0
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.71424

Number of lines 5974
 Number of pixels per line 7492
 Row of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'14"
 Longitude W000°35'48"
 Pixel number 3812
 Line number 2985

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°26'27"	W001°03'08"	261	1
2	N054°19'24"	E000°02'32"	7492	1
3	N053°55'00"	W001°14'57"	1	5974
4	N053°48'01"	W000°10'05"	7232	5974

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5975	5974
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT2 HRV2 018-244/0 30 APR 90
P

N52°15' W095°40' 24°L 12H 01MN 505 N18
BMA06944 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA06944

SPOTZ HRV1 021-239/0 17 MAR 94

N54°35'26.884" 29°P 11H 10MN 57S N1B
EMR06945 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA 06945

SPOT2 HRV1 021-240/0 17 MAR 94
P

N54°07' / W004°37' 29°R 11H 11MN 055 N1B
BMA06948 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA 06948

SPOT2 HRV2 022-239/0 17 FEB 94

N54°35'40.03"15' 19°L 11H 42MN 27S M1B
BMA06949 CCTCONTROL @CHES1994

BMA06949

SPOT3 HRV2 022-240/0 14 MAY 94
P

N54°07'W003°33' 24°L 11H 53MN 44S N1B
BMA06952 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA06952

SPOT2 HRV1 026-239/0 20 NOV 90
P

N54°35'40" 143° 14' 11H 30MN 49S N18
EMAG9953 OCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA06953

SPOT2 HRV2 026-240/0 09 NOV 91
P

N54°07'10001°39' 06°L 11H 31MN 26S N1B
BMA06955 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA 06955

SPOT2 HRV2 029-239/0 01 DEC 90
P

N54°35' / W000°45' 04"L 11H 27MN 09S N1B
BMA06956 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA06956

SPOT2 HRV2 029-240/0 05 FEB 93
P

N54°07' / W000°36' 25°R 11H 01MN 44S N18
BMA06957 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA06957

CD Number : 7001006614
Order Number : 95082428
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 25-AUG-1995 11:52:20

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	2 026-241 95/08/02 11:37:54 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 1

Project reference : S-NT-73-10-SI
Date : 19/6/95
Edition : 1
Revision : 1
Spot Image ref. : SI/DPST/D/95.170
Original Edition :

S P O T
I M A G E

Evolution of the SPOT IMAGE Standard digital products

Name and Position Date Signature

Author Philippe DELCLAUX

19/6/95

Approval

Authorization
of Application

5 rue des Satellites

B.P. 4359

F - 31030 Toulouse Cedex - FRANCE

Tel : (33) 62 19 40 40

Fax : (33) 62 19 40 56

Telex : 532 079

GENERAL BACKGROUND

The SPOT preprocessing facilities which are located in Toulouse are being upgraded in order to fulfil new requirements mainly dictated by the SPOT 4 characteristics. The new system, called CAP (for "Centre d'Archivage et de Prétraitement", which means "Archiving and Preprocessing Center") is implemented in SPOT IMAGE premises and its operation will be moved from CNES to SPOT IMAGE; as a consequence, a single location for the production activity will improve the overall performances by reducing elapsed time wasted in transferring products between two separate entities.

In addition, and as an answer to numerous users requests, the Level 1B geometric preprocessing has been improved by taking into account variations of the satellite attitude during the imaging process, and by using a correction model which will guarantee that two consecutive scenes along a same imaging segment will fit together (i.e. the overlapping portion of the two 1B scenes are fully registered).

Such modifications of the preprocessing facilities have an impact on the standard products which will be delivered by SPOT IMAGE, and particularly on the format of the digital products. A particular attention has been paid to minimize as much as possible the format evolution, and to maintain an ascending compatibility for the great majority of users. The purpose of this document is to explain these format differences.

According to the present time-schedule for starting the CAP operations, SPOT IMAGE expects beginning to deliver products with the new format by July 1995. One has to note the followings :

- the CAP system will not have the capability to produce the "old" format,
- during a certain period of time, both formats ("old" and "new") will be delivered by SPOT IMAGE, depending on the location of the archived scene. This is due to the fact that the preprocessing facilities which are operated by SSC-Satellitbild in Kiruna (Sweden) are expected to be upgraded by the end of 1995, and, until this, only the "old" format will be available from the Swedish archive. This also applies to products which have been stored in SPOT IMAGE as level 1B CCT with the "old" format, and for which it is impossible to reapply geometric corrections with the new modelization.

PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

The purpose of the document is to explain the differences between the format presently used for the digital products delivered by SPOT IMAGE (named "old" format in the following), and the format which will be used once the CAP system is in operation (named "new" format).

The "old" format is described in the document "THE SPOT STANDARD CCT FORMAT" (ref. SI/AT/85.0113).

The "new" format is described in the document "THE SPOT STANDARD DIGITAL PRODUCT FORMAT" (ref. S4-ST-73-01-CN).

MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FORMAT MODIFICATIONS

The modifications have been made with the objective of reflecting the evolutions of the products (improved level 1B geometric modelization, enhanced accuracy for several parameters, SPOT 4 additional spectral band), while keeping the "new" format very close to the "old" one in order to make the transition as smooth as possible for the users, and even fully transparent for the the big majority of them.

The format modifications fall into 3 categories :

- modification of the layout of the *Leader File* : due to the introduction of a fourth spectral band for the Multispectral mode of SPOT 4, the sequence of the records have been rearranged, starting at record number 4 (the sequence of *Leader File Descriptor*, *Header* and *Ephemeris/Attitude* records remains unchanged). The total number of records of the *Leader File* is the same (27 records). The differences between the "old" *Leader File* layout and the "new" one are described in the Table 1 hereunder,
- addition of information, either in fields which were unused (blank fields), or in already used fields by replacing blanks with significant digits (to improve accuracy), as described in the attached Table 2 (identified as "add" in the column "type"),
- modification of the content of a few fields in the only following places (identified as "mod" in Table 2, column "type"):
 - the content of the "Logical Volume ID" in the *Volume Descriptor record* has been modified to an internal reference related to the product order,
 - the information in the *Text record* (last record of the *Volume Directory* file) has been modified (it is reminded that the content of this *Text record* is just a "free-form" text intended to be displayed but not to be decoded and processed),
 - the encoding of the « instrument ID » in the *Header Record* has been changed in order to make room for future SPOT4 naming convention (HRV\$\$n\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$ instead of HRVn\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$)
 - the encoding of the "pixel size" (in line and in column) in the *Header* record has been changed to allow for 2 digits after decimal point,
 - the "satellite altitude" has been removed from the *Ephemeris/Attitude* record and replaced by the "out of range attitude indicator". The "satellite altitude" is now posted in the *Header* record, as additional field,
 - the level 1B deformation model parameters have been removed from the *Ephemeris/Attitude* record and replaced by additional parameters ; the parameters of the new level 1B modelization are encoded (in clear ASCII) in a new record named *Modelization* record,
 - each *Radiometric Calibration* record contains gains or dark current values for 1500 detectors, instead of 1000 (a set of gains or dark current values is split into 2 records (instead of 3) for one multispectral band, or into 4 records (instead of 6) for one Panchromatic band),

	bytes	type	name	old format	new format
VOLUME DIRECTORY FILE					
Volume Descriptor record:	61-76	mod	Logical vol ID	<ssn>\$<m>\$<ppbbbb>\$<v>\$	internal reference of product order
File Pointer record for Leader file :	unchanged				
File Pointer record for Imagery file :	unchanged				
File Pointer record for Trailer file :	unchanged				
Text record :	17-268	mod	free-form text		modified
LEADER FILE					
File Descriptor record:	unchanged				
Header record :	501-508 629-644 741-744 745-746 1381-1396 1397-1412 2789-3788	add mod add add mod mod add	spare instrument ID spare spare pixel size in line pixel size in column reserved	blanks HRVn\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$ blanks blanks coded \$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$PP coded \$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$PP	altitude of the satellite HRV\$\$n\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$ focus mechanism step number indicator of HRV coupled mode coded \$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$PP.PP coded \$\$\$\$\$\$\$\$PP.PP special products, SAT parameters [and simplified location model]
Ephemeris - Attitude record :	21-56 57-92 93-120 921-922 947-958 959-960 961-964 965-994 3001-3032 3033-3064 3065-3112 3113-3208 3209-3360 3361-3384 3385-3432	add add add add mod mod mod add mod mod mod mod add add add	satellite position velocity vector Universal Time spare spare & sat. altitude satellite altitude satellite altitude time of scene center level 1B def. model level 1B def. model level 1B def. model level 1B def. model spare spare spare	±XXXX.XXX\$\$\$, ±YYY.....etc... ±X.XXXXXX\$\$\$, ±Y.YY.....etc... DDDDSSSSSS\$\$\$\$...\$\$\$ blanks blanks & 2 digits of altitude value altitude value (next 2 digits) altitude value (last 4 digits) encoded with 14 digits (milli sec) ((bytes 991 to 994 blanked) deformation model deformation model deformation model deformation model & blanks blanks blanks blanks	±XXXX.XXXX\$\$\$, ±YYY.....etc... ±X.XXXXXX\$\$\$, ±Y.YY.....etc... DDDDSSSSSS,SSSSSS\$\$\$\$...\$ flag indicating use of Doris (SPOT4) line period (milliseconds) out of range attitude indicator blanks encoded with 17 digits (micro sec) ((addition of bytes 991 to 994) value of first attitude angles value of last attitude angles HRV lock angles (same as bytes 2461 [-2492, but with 1/100 s accuracy) look angles for SWIR band (SPOT 4) blanks or orbital bulletin (SPOT 4) major frame counter values at scene [begin, and segment begin & end. On board time and UT relations

Table 2 : FIELD MODIFICATIONS

Project reference : S-NT-73-10-SI
Date : 19/6/95
Edition : 1
Revision : 1

Evolution of the
SPOT IMAGE Standard
digital products

SPOT IMAGE

Page 4

	bytes	type	name	old format	new format
LEADER FILE (cont'd)					
Radiometric calibration records :	49-56 2061-3060	add add	spare spare	blanks blanks	relative calibration date 500 additional gains or dark currents
Modelization record :	1-16 17-80 81-192 193-336 337-688 689-864 865-960	add add add add add add add	<i>new record</i> <i>new record</i> <i>new record</i> <i>new record</i> <i>new record</i> <i>new record</i> <i>new record</i>	<i>not existing</i> <i>not existing</i> <i>not existing</i> <i>not existing</i> <i>not existing</i> <i>not existing</i> <i>not existing</i>	record description scene position in the segment attitude model coordinates normalization coefficients direct level 1B model coefficients reverse level 1B model coefficients SWIR registration model
Ground control points record :	<i>unchanged</i>				
Histogram records :	2092-2102 2103-2246 2471-2486 2487-2818 2819-2822	mod mod add add add	film recording deconvolution coef. radiometric stretching spectral responses solar responses	film recording parameters 2 sets of 7 coefficients blanks blanks blanks	blanks 2 sets of 9 coefficients lower & upper thresholds spectral responses for each band normal solar equivalent irradiances
Map projection record :	<i>unchanged</i>				
Annotations record :		mod	annotations on films	text to be written on photo products	new text for photo products
IMAGERY FILE					
File descriptor record :	<i>unchanged</i>				
Image data record :	21-24	mod	time of scan line	time of the scan line	Major Frame count
TRAILER FILE					
File descriptor record :	<i>unchanged</i>				
Trailer - quality record :	<i>unchanged</i>				
Geometric transformations record :	21-1080	mod	geometric models	geometric transformations	blanks
Grid rectification record :	<i>removed</i>	mod			

Table 2 (cont'd) : FIELD MODIFICATIONS

NOTE D'INFORMATION

Nouveau format des scènes SPOT

S P O T
I M A G E

Géré, depuis le lancement du satellite SPOT 1, par le C.N.E.S. (l'agence française de l'espace) au sein du CRIS, (Centre de Rectification des Images Spatiales), l'archivage des données SPOT - et surtout la fabrication des produits - sont désormais pris en charge par la société Spot Image depuis le 2 août 1995. Spot Image a créé à cet effet dans ses locaux toulousains un nouveau centre de production : le CAP (Centre d'Archivage et de Prétraitement).

La mise en service opérationnelle du CAP constitue une étape importante vers la prise en charge progressive par Spot Image de l'exploitation du système SPOT directement en relation avec sa mission commerciale. Pour l'utilisateur, ce changement se traduit par des délais de livraison raccourcis ainsi que par une modification du format des scènes SPOT de niveaux 1A, 1AP, 1B, 2A.

L'objectif principal de ce changement de format est de permettre au CAP de prendre en compte les spécificités du futur satellite SPOT 4, en particulier l'ajout d'une quatrième bande spectrale Moyen Infra-Rouge (MIR).

A cette occasion et afin de satisfaire de nombreuses demandes, le niveau de prétraitement 1B a été amélioré afin de rendre possible le raccordement direct de deux images consécutives d'un même segment de prise de vues.

Il convient de noter que certains centres de production n'intégreront pas immédiatement cette nouvelle chaîne de traitement et, en particulier, le centre opéré par la société suédoise SSC Satellitbild à Kiruna (Suède), qui se dotera d'équipements similaires au début de l'année 1996. De ce fait, pendant plusieurs mois, il vous arrivera de recevoir des produits à l'ancien et au nouveau formats.

Néanmoins, soucieux de minimiser l'impact de ces modifications, Spot Image a volontairement limité leur nombre et a porté une attention particulière au maintien d'une compatibilité ascendante pour la grande majorité des utilisateurs.

Votre correspondant habituel au Service Clientèle se tient à votre disposition pour tout complément d'information, et pour vous faire parvenir une documentation technique décrivant les évolutions du format de même qu'un CD-Rom de démonstration contenant des scènes SPOT à l'ancien et au nouveau formats. Spot Image met également à votre disposition une "hot line" technique aux numéros suivants : tél. (33) 62.19.42.42 - facsimile (33) 62.19.40.56, afin de vous aider à résoudre d'éventuels problèmes concernant la prise en compte informatique de ce nouveau format.

Comment reconnaître le nouveau format :

Le premier enregistrement des deuxième, troisième et quatrième fichiers ("LEADER File", "IMAGERY File" et "TRAILER File") est appelé "FILE DESCRIPTOR". Ces trois enregistrements contiennent un champ (octets 17 à 28) identifiant le document qui spécifie le format.

Dans le nouveau format, ce champ de 12 caractères contient le texte : S4-ST-73-1CN.

(Dans l'ancien format, il valait : S-ST-73-1-CN.)

Un test sur les deux premiers caractères de ce champ permettra de différencier le nouveau format de l'ancien :

"S-" --> ancien format

"S4-" --> nouveau format

MEMO FOR INFORMATION

New SPOT scene format

S P O T
I M A G E

From the time of the SPOT 1 satellite's launch, the French space agency CNES handled not only the archiving of all SPOT data, but, more importantly, the production of all standard products within the CRIS Space Imagery Preprocessing Centre. On 2 August 1995, these duties were transferred to Spot Image, with its new purpose built Archiving and Preprocessing Centre (CAP) located in the company's head office building in Toulouse.

The operational commissioning of the CAP represents another milestone in gradually shifting control for system operations having a direct impact on the company's distribution and marketing mission from CNES to Spot Image. For the user, this shift means faster service and a change in the format of level 1A, 1AP, 1B and 2A SPOT scenes.

The main purpose of this change in format is to allow the CAP to take into account the peculiarities of the future SPOT 4 satellite, particularly the addition of a fourth, Mid-Infrared (MIR), spectral band.

In view of this addition and in order to satisfy numerous requests, the 1B preprocessing level has been improved so that it is now possible to join two consecutive images from the same data strip directly.

It should be noted that some production centres will not integrate this new processing cycle immediately, especially the Kiruna centre run by the Swedish company SSC Satellitbild. Kiruna will be fitted out with similar facilities early in 1996. For this reason, *over a period of several months, you may receive products in both old and new formats.*

Nonetheless, in order to minimize the effect of these changes, Spot Image has purposely limited the amount and has been careful to make sure that the vast majority of users will continue to benefit from the upward compatibility of products.

Your usual contact in the Customer Department will be pleased to give you whatever further information you may require and to send you both some technical documentation describing the changes in format and a demonstration CD-ROM containing SPOT scenes in both old and new formats. SPOT IMAGE also operates a technical hot line on the following numbers: tel.: (33) 62 19 42 42 and fax: (33) 62 19 40 56 so as to help you resolve any problems that might arise with data processing due to the change in format.

Recognising the new format :

The first recording of the second, third and fourth files (LEADER File, IMAGERY File and TRAILER File) is known as the FILE DESCRIPTOR. These three recording contain a field (bytes 17 to 28) which identifies the document that specifies the format.

In the new format, this 12-character field contains the following text: S4-ST-73-1CN.
(In the old format, it contained: S-ST-73-1-CN).

The new format may be distinguished from the old simply by examining the first two characters in this field:

"S-" = old format

"S4" = new format.

CONTROLE QUALITE IMAGE

K./Sat 26 241/0
Date 2/8/1995
Time 11:37:53
Sat S2
Ins HRV 1
Mode P
Level NIV 10
Incidence 18.10'41"
Center N53.39'10"
W2.41'12"
Order 0000199508242801

BCNES 1995

Work order : 9508242801
 Volume ID : 7001006614
 Scene ID : 2 026-241 95/08/02 11:37:54 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 25-AUG-1995 11:52:12

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 026-241 95/08/02 11:37:54 1 P
 K-J Identification 026-241
 Date 95/08/02
 Time 11 h 37 mn 54 s
 Instrument HRV 1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 018.0 Degres
 Incidence angle L18.2 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: 166.4 Elevation: 054.0
 Gain Number 8
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.62277

Number of lines 6011
 Number of pixels per line 6824
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°39'19"
 Longitude W0-1°18'47"
 Pixel number 3370
 Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°59'56"	W0-1°37'40"	222	1
2	N053°48'51"	W00-°40'24"	6824	1
3	N053°29'26"	W0-1°56'10"	1	6011
4	N053°18'29"	W00-°59'31"	6602	6011

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6012	6011
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

CD Number : 700006675
Order Number : 95082428
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 31-AUG-1995 09:07:48

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	02	Scene std.	1 021-235 88/10/31 11:10:20 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 1

Work order : 9508242802
 CD number : 7000006675
 Scene ID : 1 21-235 88/10/31 11:10:20 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 30-AUG-1995 16:47:17

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 21-235 88/10/31 11:10:20 2 P
 K-J Identification 21-235
 Date 88/10/31
 Time 11 h 10 mn 20 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 010.7 Degres
 Incidence angle R26.5 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +168.5 Elevation: 018.7
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94798

Number of lines 5971
 Number of pixels per line 7633
 Row of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N056°25'50"
 Longitude W002°55'39"
 Pixel number 3889
 Line number 2983

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N056°45'12"	W003°25'22"	245	1
2	N056°37'48"	W002°14'18"	7633	1
3	N056°13'47"	W003°37'57"	1	5971
4	N056°06'28"	W002°27'49"	7389	5971

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5972	5971
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT1 HRV2 021-235/0 31 OCT 88
P

N56°26' / W002°56' 26°R 11H 10MN 205 N1B
82521008 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

ВНА М140

CD Number : 7000007153
Order Number : 95082428
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 25-AUG-1995 13:57:09

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	03	Scene std.	3 022-243 95/06/29 11:49:45 2 P Level 1B SAT 1
2	04	Scene std.	1 024-246 89/07/16 11:50:17 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 2

MEMO FOR INFORMATION

New SPOT scene format

S P O T
I M A G E

From the time of the SPOT 1 satellite's launch, the French space agency CNES handled not only the archiving of all SPOT data, but, more importantly, the production of all standard products within the CRIS Space Imagery Preprocessing Centre. On 2 August 1995, these duties were transferred to Spot Image, with its new purpose built Archiving and Preprocessing Centre (CAP) located in the company's head office building in Toulouse.

The operational commissioning of the CAP represents another milestone in gradually shifting control for system operations having a direct impact on the company's distribution and marketing mission from CNES to Spot Image. For the user, this shift means faster service and a change in the format of level 1A, 1AP, 1B and 2A SPOT scenes.

The main purpose of this change in format is to allow the CAP to take into account the peculiarities of the future SPOT 4 satellite, particularly the addition of a fourth, Mid-Infrared (MIR), spectral band.

In view of this addition and in order to satisfy numerous requests, the 1B preprocessing level has been improved so that it is now possible to join two consecutive images from the same data strip directly.

It should be noted that some production centres will not integrate this new processing cycle immediately, especially the Kiruna centre run by the Swedish company SSC Satellitbild. Kiruna will be fitted out with similar facilities early in 1996. For this reason, *over a period of several months, you may receive products in both old and new formats.*

Nonetheless, in order to minimize the effect of these changes, Spot Image has purposely limited the amount and has been careful to make sure that the vast majority of users will continue to benefit from the upward compatibility of products.

Your usual contact in the Customer Department will be pleased to give you whatever further information you may require and to send you both some technical documentation describing the changes in format and a demonstration CD-ROM containing SPOT scenes in both old and new formats. SPOT IMAGE also operates a technical hot line on the following numbers: tel.: (33) 62 19 42 42 and fax: (33) 62 19 40 56 so as to help you resolve any problems that might arise with data processing due to the change in format.

Recognising the new format :

The first recording of the second, third and fourth files (LEADER File, IMAGERY File and TRAILER File) is known as the FILE DESCRIPTOR. These three recording contain a field (bytes 17 to 28) which identifies the document that specifies the format.

In the new format, this 12-character field contains the following text: S4-ST-73-1CN.
(In the old format, it contained: S-ST-73-1-CN).

The new format may be distinguished from the old simply by examining the first two characters in this field:

"S-" = old format
"S4" = new format.

NOTE D'INFORMATION

Nouveau format des scènes SPOT

S P O T
I M A G E

Géré, depuis le lancement du satellite SPOT 1, par le C.N.E.S. (l'agence française de l'espace) au sein du CRIS, (Centre de Rectification des Images Spatiales), l'archivage des données SPOT - et surtout la fabrication des produits - sont désormais pris en charge par la société Spot Image depuis le 2 août 1995. Spot Image a créé à cet effet dans ses locaux toulousains un nouveau centre de production : le CAP (Centre d'Archivage et de Prétraitement).

La mise en service opérationnelle du CAP constitue une étape importante vers la prise en charge progressive par Spot Image de l'exploitation du système SPOT directement en relation avec sa mission commerciale. Pour l'utilisateur, ce changement se traduit par des délais de livraison raccourcis ainsi que par une modification du format des scènes SPOT de niveaux 1A, 1AP, 1B, 2A.

L'objectif principal de ce changement de format est de permettre au CAP de prendre en compte les spécificités du futur satellite SPOT 4, en particulier l'ajout d'une quatrième bande spectrale Moyen Infra-Rouge (MIR).

A cette occasion et afin de satisfaire de nombreuses demandes, le niveau de prétraitement 1B a été amélioré afin de rendre possible le raccordement direct de deux images consécutives d'un même segment de prise de vues.

Il convient de noter que certains centres de production n'intégreront pas immédiatement cette nouvelle chaîne de traitement et, en particulier, le centre opéré par la société suédoise SSC Satellitbild à Kiruna (Suède), qui se dotera d'équipements similaires au début de l'année 1996. De ce fait, pendant plusieurs mois, il vous arrivera de recevoir des produits à l'ancien et au nouveau formats.

Néanmoins, soucieux de minimiser l'impact de ces modifications, Spot Image a volontairement limité leur nombre et a porté une attention particulière au maintien d'une compatibilité ascendante pour la grande majorité des utilisateurs.

Votre correspondant habituel au Service Clientèle se tient à votre disposition pour tout complément d'information, et pour vous faire parvenir une documentation technique décrivant les évolutions du format de même qu'un CD-Rom de démonstration contenant des scènes SPOT à l'ancien et au nouveau formats. Spot Image met également à votre disposition une "hot line" technique aux numéros suivants : tél. (33) 62.19.42.42 - facsimile (33) 62.19.40.56, afin de vous aider à résoudre d'éventuels problèmes concernant la prise en compte informatique de ce nouveau format.

Comment reconnaître le nouveau format :

Le premier enregistrement des deuxième, troisième et quatrième fichiers ("LEADER File", "IMAGERY File" et "TRAILER File") est appelé "FILE DESCRIPTOR". Ces trois enregistrements contiennent un champ (octets 17 à 28) identifiant le document qui spécifie le format.

Dans le nouveau format, ce champ de 12 caractères contient le texte : S4-ST-73-1CN.

(Dans l'ancien format, il valait : S-ST-73-1-CN.)

Un test sur les deux premiers caractères de ce champ permettra de différencier le nouveau format de l'ancien :

"S-" --> ancien format

"S4-" --> nouveau format

Work order : 9508242804
CD number : 7000007153
Scene ID : 1 24-246 89/07/16 11:50:17 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 25-AUG-1995 11:48:29

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 24-246 89/07/16 11:50:17 2 P
K-J identification 24-246
Date 89/07/16
Time 11 h 50 mn 17 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 018.3 Degres
Incidence angle L25.4 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +165.4 Elevation: 059.7
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.92441

Number of lines 6014
Number of pixels per line 7484
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°18'44"
Longitude W004°01'47"
Pixel number 3674
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°39'56"	W004°21'57"	229	1
2	N051°27'33"	W003°22'25"	7484	1
3	N051°09'28"	W004°39'48"	1	6014
4	N050°57'15"	W003°40'51"	7256	6014

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6015	6014
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT1 HRV2 024-246/0 16 JUL 89
P

NS1°19'0004°02' 25°L 11H 50MN 17S N1B
BTA16453 CCTCONTROL @CNES1989

BNA 07051

Work order : 9508242803
 CD number : 7000007153
 Scene ID : 3 22-243 95/06/29 11:49:45 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 25-AUG-1995 11:50:40

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 3 22-243 95/06/29 11:49:45 2 P
 K-J identification 22-243
 Date 95/06/29
 Time 11 h 49 mn 45 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 1
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 018.2 Degres
 Incidence angle L22.0 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.5 Elevation: 060.2
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01:55375

Number of lines 6012
 Number of pixels per line 7147
 Row of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°40'14"
 Longitude W003°57'49"
 Pixel number 3519
 Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°01'08"	W004°17'20"	231	1
2	N052°49'23"	W003°18'47"	7147	1
3	N052°30'41"	W004°35'40"	1	6012
4	N052°19'05"	W003°37'43"	6917	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT3 HRV2 022-243/1 29 JUN 95

P

N52°40' W883°58' 22°L 11H 49M 46S N1B
BMA10948 CCTCONTROL @CNES1995

BMA 10948

CD Number : 7000008659

Date : 11-MAR-1996 08:75:39

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	1 026-240 90/12/05 10:59:54 1 P Level 1B

Work order : 9603080404
 CD number : 7000008659
 Scene ID : 1 26-240 90/12/05 10:59:54 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 11-MAR-1996 08:57:39

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 26-240 90/12/05 10:59:54 1 P
 K-J identification 26-240
 Date 90/12/05
 Time 10 h 59 mn 54 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 009.5 Degrees
 Incidence angle R29.7 Degrees
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +166.4 Elevation: 012.8
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.59578

Number of lines 5967
 Number of pixels per line 8065
 Row of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'13"
 Longitude W001°42'14"
 Pixel number 4120
 Line number 2981

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°26'25"	W002°12'52"	265	1
2	N054°19'28"	W001°01'50"	8065	1
3	N053°54'54"	W002°23'48"	1	5967
4	N053°48'01"	W001°13'39"	7801	5967

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5968	5967
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT1 HRV1 026-240/0 05 DEC 90

P

N54°07' / W001°42' 29°R 10H 59MN 54S N1B
BMA08124 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BNA08124

CD Number : 7001008820

Date : 11-MAR-1996 09:55:47

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	1 026-239 90/12/05 10:59:46 1 P Level 1B HRV 1
2	02	Scene std.	2 029-239 93/02/05 11:01:36 2 P Level 1B HRV 2
3	03	Scene std.	1 026-239 90/12/05 10:59:45 2 P Level 1B HRV 2
4	04	Scene std.	1 026-240 90/12/05 10:59:53 2 P Level 1B HRV 2

Work order : 9603080402
 Volume ID : 7001008820
 Scene ID : 1 026-239 90/12/05 10:59:46 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 11-MAR-1996 09:55:47

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 026-239 90/12/05 10:59:46 1 P
 K-J identification 026-239
 Date 90/12/05
 Time 10 h 59 mn 46 s
 Instrument HRV 1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 009.6 Degres
 Incidence angle R29.7 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: 166.6 Elevation: 012.4
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.59578

Number of lines 5966
 Number of pixels per line 8061
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'05"
 Longitude W0-1°32'04"
 Pixel number 4117
 Line number 2983

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°54'18"	W0-2°03'01"	261	1
2	N054°47'18"	W00-°51'11"	8061	1
3	N054°22'48"	W0-2°14'08"	1	5966
4	N054°15'52"	W0-1°03'12"	7800	5966

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5967	5966
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9603080401
 Volume ID : 7001008820
 Scene ID : 2 029-239 93/02/05 11:01:36 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 11-MAR-1996 09:54:27

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 029-239 93/02/05 11:01:36 2 P
 K-J identification 029-239
 Date 93/02/05
 Time 11 h 01 mn 36 s
 Instrument HRV 2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 010.5 Degrees
 Incidence angle R25.1 Degrees
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: 161.4 Elevation: 017.6
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.71424

Number of lines 5973
 Number of pixels per line 7489
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'05"
 Longitude W00°24'52"
 Pixel number 3810
 Line number 2987

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°54'20"	W00°52'28"	258	1
2	N054°47'13"	E000°13'56"	7489	1
3	N054°22'54"	W0-1°04'28"	1	5973
4	N054°15'51"	E000°01'06"	7231	5973

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5974	5973
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9603080403
 Volume ID : 7001008820
 Scene ID : 1 026-239 90/12/05 10:59:45 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 11-MAR-1996 09:57:06

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 026-239 90/12/05 10:59:45 2 P
 K-J Identification 026-239
 Date 90/12/05
 Time 10 h 59 mn 45 s
 Instrument HRV 2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 010.1 Degres
 Incidence angle R27.2 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: 167.1 Elevation: 012.4
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.55526

Number of lines 5970
 Number of pixels per line 7725
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°35'05"
 Longitude W00°54'43"
 Pixel number 3937
 Line number 2985

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°54'19"	W0-1°23'44"	256	1
2	N054°47'14"	W00-°15'04"	7725	1
3	N054°22'51"	W0-1°35'21"	1	5970
4	N054°15'50"	W00-°27'32"	7469	5970

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5971	5970
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9603080405
 Volume ID : 7001008820
 Scene ID : 1 026-240 90/12/05 10:59:53 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 11-MAR-1996 09:58:27

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 026-240 90/12/05 10:59:53 2 P
 K-J identification 026-240
 Date 90/12/05
 Time 10 h 59 mn 53 s
 Instrument HRV 2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 010.0 Degres
 Incidence angle R27.2 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: 167.0 Elevation: 012.9
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.55526

Number of lines 5971
 Number of pixels per line 7727
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N054°07'13"
 Longitude W0-1°05'19"
 Pixel number 3938
 Line number 2985

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N054°26'26"	W0-1°34'02"	259	1
2	N054°19'24"	W00-°26'08"	7727	1
3	N053°54'57"	W0-1°45'28"	1	5971
4	N053°48'00"	W00-°38'24"	7468	5971

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5972	5971
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

CONTROL QUALITE IMAGI

K J/Sat 29 219/0
Date 1993 2 5
Time 11:1:36
Sat S2
Ins HRV 2
Mode P
Level HV_10
Incidence -26.52° 31"
Contour 054.15° 5"
H1.35° 8"
Order 0000199603080101

©CNES 1993

CONTROL QUALITY IMAGE

K J/Sat 26 219/0
Date 1990-12-5
Time 10:59:46
Sat S1
Ins HRV 1
Mode P
Level HV 10
Incidence 30.18° 55"
Center 054.35° 4"
02.27° 55"
Order 0000199603080402

JCNES 1990

▼
CONTROLE QUALITE IMAGE

K J/Sat 26 219/0
Date 1990-12-5
Time 10:59:45
Sat S1
Ins HRV 2
Mode P
Level HRV III
Incidence 28.47° 41"
Contor 054.35° 4"
01.5° 16"
Order 0000199603080403

SCNES 1990

CONTROLE QUALITE IMAGE

K J/Sat 26 240/0
Date 1990 12 5
Time 10:59:53
Sat S1
Inn HRV 2
Mode P
Level HV 18
Incidence 28.47° 43"
Center 854.7° 17"
W2.54° 41"
Order 0000199603080405

©CNES 1990

